

Transferability in Optimization Via Multi-Domain Hyper-Heuristics

Etor Arza, Ekhiñe Irurozki, Josu Ceberio, Aritz Pérez

APPENDIX A NEUROEVOLUTION OF AUGMENTING TOPOLOGIES

In this paper, the neural networks were trained with a reinforcement learning, neuroevolution algorithm. More specifically, neuroevolution of augmenting topologies (NEAT) has been used¹. Introduced by Stanley et al. [1], NEAT is a genetic algorithm for neural networks that can evolve not only the parameters (weights) of a neural network but also its structure.

NEAT is one of the most influential approaches in the field of neuroevolution to date. In fact, before the introduction of NEAT, most of the neuroevolution techniques without a fixed topology suffered from the competing conventions problem [2]. When two networks have similar functionality but are entirely different, and thus, incompatible structures, we say that these two networks contain competing conventions. NEAT is a revolutionary neuroevolution technique because it defined a new way to efficiently handle the competing conventions problem through a novel speciation mechanism. Specifically, each time NEAT introduces a new structure due to a mutation, this new structure is assigned a unique innovation number. Then, these innovation numbers are used to 1) select individuals that are sufficiently similar to each other for crossover and 2) only perform crossover in the parts of the structure that have the same innovation numbers.

While early studies on the subject suggest that fixed topology networks perform worse than their counterparts [3], there are now promising alternatives that have been found to outperform NEAT even with a fixed topology [4], [5]. New trends in neuroevolution include integrating the Covariance Matrix Adaptation metaheuristic to the framework of neuroevolution [6], designing the architecture of deep neural networks with evolutionary algorithms [7], [8] and HyperNeat [9], in which a two dimension real function is learned that represents the weights of a neural network, achieving a more compact representation that takes into account the position of the neural

network links. In this paper, the NEAT algorithm with node and edge removal is used for two reasons: 1) NEAT is a simple yet well-tested neuroevolution algorithm, and 2) the component removal allows the network to adapt its size to the time consumed in the evaluation of the neural network.

To achieve this, one only needs to set a maximum runtime as the stopping criterion for the hyper-heuristic solver during the training step and make sure the evaluation time of the solutions is negligible with respect to the evaluation time of the network. The preference towards smaller networks is achieved implicitly: smaller networks are processed faster, and so the hyper-heuristic performs more function evaluations in the same amount of time, possibly obtaining better performance.

APPENDIX B DETAILED EXPLANATION OF THE *modify* PROCESS

This appendix includes a complete explanation of how the function *modify* (line 14 in Algorithm 2 in the main manuscript) modifies a solution σ_i . Algorithm 1 shows the pseudo-code of how this modification is applied in detail. The modification towards a reference (lines 2-3) tries to modify the permutation into another permutation that is one unit of distance nearer the reference [10]. The distance is defined for each operator as the minimum number of applications of that operator to transform one permutation into the other permutation [10]. A modification away from the reference is defined similarly (line 5), but choosing the parameters of the operator such that the distance between the reference permutation and the modified permutation is increased by one unit. Finally, after the modification is applied (line 7), the objective value of the solution is measured, and a worse candidate is only accepted with probability $1 - \text{prob_accept_worse}$ (lines 8-10).

Etor Arza, Ekhiñe Irurozki, and Aritz Pérez are with the Basque Center for Applied Mathematics (BCAM)

Josu Ceberio is with the Department of Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence at the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU)

Manuscript submitted May 8, 2023.

¹The source code, along with all the experimentation is available at the GitHub repository <https://github.com/EtorArza/TransfHH>. The neuroevolution algorithm was taken from the *accneat* package, with a few minor changes made to it. *Accneat* is a fork of Stanley et al.'s [1] implementation with some improvements, such as delete mutations and speed improvements, available at <https://github.com/sean-dougherty/accneat>. The code provided alongside this paper also uses parts of other software projects, see the LICENCE file in the repository for a comprehensive list.

Algorithm 1: modify(σ_i , σ_{ref} , direction, operator, prob_accept_worse)

Input:
 σ_i : The permutation to be modified.
 σ_{ref} : The reference permutation.
direction: Direction of the modification.
operator: Operator of the modification.
prob_accept_worse: Probability of accepting a worse solution.

```

1 if direction = 1 then
2   create a minimum length path from  $\sigma_i$  to  $\sigma_{ref}$ , defined as the minimum
   sequence of applications of operator to solution  $\sigma_i$  that are required to
   obtain solution  $\sigma_{ref}$  (Schiavinotto et al. [10]).
3   operator_params  $\leftarrow$  parameters of the first operator in the minimum
   length path
4 else if direction = -1 then
5   operator_params  $\leftarrow$  parameters of operator that, if applied to  $\sigma_i$ , would
   increase the distance between  $\sigma_i$  and  $\sigma_{ref}$  by one. The distance is
   defined as the minimum required applications of operator to transform
    $\sigma_i$  into  $\sigma_{ref}$ .
6 end
7  $\sigma_{cand} \leftarrow$  create candidate solution by applying operator once with
   parameters operator_params to solution  $\sigma_i$ 
8 if objective value  $\sigma_i$  is better than objective value  $\sigma_{cand}$  then
9   with probability (1 - prob_accept_worse)
10     $\sigma_{cand} \leftarrow \sigma_i$ 
11 end
12 return  $\sigma_{cand}$ 

```

APPENDIX C TRANSFERABILITY

In this appendix, we formally define the transferability and give additional details on how to generate the embedding based on the performance of the hyper-heuristic. For additional details, we refer the interested reader to the GitHub repository with the source code.

A. Transferability matrix

We begin by introducing some notation to formally define this concept.

Notation 1: Controller trained in a problem

Let A_1 be an optimization problem and φ a controller. We denote that φ was trained in problem A_1 as φ_1 .

Definition 1: Performance of a controller

Let A_1, A_2 be two optimization problems and φ_1 a controller trained in optimization problem A_1 . We define the performance of φ_1 on A_2 , as the result of optimizing A_2 with the proposed hyper-heuristic algorithm, using φ_1 as the controller and we denote it as $\varphi_1(A_2)$.

Definition 2: Transferability

Let A_1, \dots, A_k be k maximization problems² and φ_i, φ_j two controllers trained in the problems A_i, A_j respectively. We define the transferability from problem A_i to problem A_j , $T(A_i \rightarrow A_j)$, as the normalized rank in performance that the hyper-heuristic guided by controller φ_1 has in problem A_2 . Formally,

$$T(A_i \rightarrow A_j) = \frac{r_{i,j}}{k-1}$$

²We assume that all problems considered are maximization problems. Specifically, minimization problems have been transformed into maximization problems by redefining the problem as a maximization of the objective function when multiplied by -1 .

where $r_{i,j}$ is the ranking (best to worst) of $\varphi_i(A_j)$ in $\{\varphi_t(A_j)\}_{t=1,\dots,k}$. In other words, $T(A_i \rightarrow A_j)$ is assigned a rank proportional to how well controller φ_i does on problem A_j with respect to the performance of the rest of the controllers in the same problem. The transferability $T(A_i \rightarrow A_j)$ is 0 if φ_i is the controller with the best performance in A_j and 1 if it is the worst performing.

Notation 2: Transferability Matrix

Let A_1, \dots, A_k be k maximization problems. We denote the transferability matrix as T where each element $T_{i,j}$ is $T(A_i \rightarrow A_j)$.

The transferability matrix can be further improved by reordering the problems in problem set. Specifically, we reorder the optimization problems such that the loss

$$L = \sum_{j=1}^k \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} (T_{i,j} - T_{i+1,j})^2} + \sum_{i=1}^k \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{k-1} (T_{i,j} - T_{i+1,j})^2}$$

is minimized. Minimizing this loss implies that adjacent columns and rows in the transferability matrix are as similar as possible to each other.

B. Repeated measurements and noise

It is important to measure the transferability several times and average the results. The reason is that it is very likely that stochastic optimization algorithms will get different scores each time they are tested. Without this repetition step, it is possible to observe transferability, when in reality, is just due to the random nature of the optimization algorithms. This is better understood with the following example.

Let us assume that the transferability of a random search algorithm is measured in problem set i). Since the random search algorithm has no learning phase, the score will be random each time. When we measure the transferability only once, we get what is shown in Figure 1a. Notice that $T_{3,2} = 0$. From that, it would be erroneous to conclude that the problem A_3 is good at training the random search algorithm for problem A_2 . In fact, $T_{3,2} = 0$ has the same probability as $T_{i,2} = 0$, for all $i = 1, \dots, 12$.

On the other hand, if we average 10 repeated measures of the transferability, we obtain the results shown in Figure 1b. In this figure, we see that most of the values are near 0.5. The interpretation is that there was no transferability: it does not matter which instance is used during the training step. In short, several repeated measurements overcome the limitation of observing transferability in stochastic algorithms when there should be none. For this reason, in the rest of the paper, we averaged 10 measurements of the transferability.

1) Related work: Hong et al. [11] proposed measuring the transferability as the average objective value of the hyper-heuristic when training and testing two *problem classes*. Their experimental approach is different, as they study the *transferability among problem classes* instead of *transferability among problems*. They use *problem class* to refer to an infinite

(a) One measurement.

(b) Ten measurements.

Figure 1: The transferability of a random search algorithm with one measurement (a) and with ten averaged measurements (b).

set of optimization problems parameterized by one or more real values (for example, $f(x) = ax^2$, with the parameter $a \in [1, 2]$).

Our experimental setup on transferability improves the methodology of Hong et al. [11] in four key aspects. Firstly, by defining the transferability with ranks instead of objective values, we can compare the values across different problems. When objective values are used directly, the differences are not comparable³.

Secondly, by repeating several measurements of the transferability and computing the average ranks, we can distinguish between noise and the actual difference in performance (this is not possible with average objective values). Additional details on *repeated measurements* are given in Appendix C-B.

Thirdly, we experimentally show that the analysis carried out with our approach is correlated with the properties of the optimization problems, which suggests that the proposed technique is useful to find similarities and differences in the properties of optimization problems. Finally, we show that our approach works in both the combinatorial and continuous domains, while the approach of Hong et al. [11] was only

³For example, let us assume we have the optimization problems $f_1(x) = x^2$ and $f_2(x) = 10^{10} \cdot x^2$ both defined in the interval $[0, 1]$. Given two solutions, if the difference in objective value is 0.5, in problem f_1 it would be considered a bigger difference than in problem f_2 .

shown to work in the continuous domain.

APPENDIX D RESPONSE

In the previous section, we proposed an embedding for a set of optimization problems via the performance of the hyper-heuristic. In this section, we propose another embedding by focusing instead on the behavior of the hyper-heuristic.

1) *Defining the response:* The behavior of the hyper-heuristic, how it performs the optimization, is determined by every response Y (the output) of the neural network, generated during the optimization: the decoder modifies each solution according to its corresponding response Y . Therefore, it makes sense to summarize the behavior of the hyper-heuristic in an optimization problem by averaging every response Y that the neural network produces when solving the problem.

Definition 3: Response

Let A_1, A_2 be two problems. We define the response from A_1 to A_2 , $R(A_1 \rightarrow A_2)$, as the average of all response Y generated⁴ when solving problem A_2 , with a neural network obtained by training the hyper-heuristic in problem A_1 . The response can be interpreted as a summary of the behavior of the hyper-heuristic when solving problem A_2 with a controller trained in problem A_1 .

The response is a random variable in the sense that two independent computations of the response will not produce the same result. The response depends on two factors that cannot be fixed or predicted, the first one a) is related to the training stage, and the second b), is related to the testing stage. Firstly a), two executions of the neuroevolution algorithm on the same problem will (almost) never produce two identical neural networks. Secondly b), due to the probabilistic nature of the hyper-heuristic, two executions on the same problem with the same neural network are likely to diverge into a different final solution. This is in part due to the random initialization of the population. Luckily, variability regarding b) is easy to overcome by averaging the response of many executions of the hyper-heuristic in the same test problem.

The variability introduced during training a) is determined by the random seed used to train the neural network. Therefore, each observation of the response can be notated as $R(i, j, s)$ where i denotes the training problem, j denotes the test problem, and s denotes the random seed. An observation of the response, hence, averages several measurements of the response in the same test problem.

To find out what determines the variability in response, we measured the average distance between two responses

$$\|R(i_1, j_1, s_1) - R(i_2, j_2, s_2)\|_1$$

⁴The response-hyper-heuristic behavior mapping is not always injective, and depends on the implementation of the decoder. The decoder for permutation problems proposed in this paper is not injective. In other words: two controllers with different responses may produce the same behavior in the decoder. A possible solution is to transform the output so that injectivity is preserved. These transformations are simple functions, such as the indicator function $\chi_{(0, 25, 1]}$. For more details on the exact functions used to reduce the duplicity, we refer the interested reader to the source code provided.

Average L1 distance between two responses

Case	1)	2)	3)	4)
Train problem	same	same	different	different
Test problem	different	different	same	different
Training seed	same	different		
Problem set				
i)	0.050	0.436	0.516	0.520
ii)	0.004	0.371	0.367	0.370
iii)	0.174	2.718	2.832	2.812
iv)	0.181	3.172	3.122	3.182

Table I: Average distance between two responses trained in the same problem (with or without the same seed) and tested in the same problem.

in these four cases:

- 1) $i_1 = i_2$, $j_1 \neq j_2$ and $s_1 = s_2$
- 2) $i_1 = i_2$, $j_1 \neq j_2$ and $s_1 \neq s_2$
- 3) $i_1 \neq i_2$, $j_1 = j_2$ and $s_1 \neq s_2$
- 4) $i_1 \neq i_2$, $j_1 \neq j_2$ and $s_1 \neq s_2$

for the four problem sets i) - iv) as defined in Section IV-A.

As seen in Table I case 1), the distance is really small when the same training problem & training seed is used (even if tested in different problems). In addition, the distance is much larger in the rest of the cases. The interpretation is that, given the training problem i and the random seed s , the response of the hyper-heuristic is determined (disregarding some small variability associated with the test instance j).

Consequently, it makes sense to model the response as a function $R(i, s) = k^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^k R(i, j, s)$. For each problem i , we have 10 samples of the behavior of the hyper-heuristic $R(i, s)$ in that problem (one for each seed s). Notice that the response modeled like this depends on the training problem. Now we want to see if there is any correlation between the behavior of the hyper-heuristic and the optimization problem used to train it, regardless of the training seed.

A naive approach to achieve this would be to average all the responses in one problem $R(i) = 10^{-1} \sum_{s=1}^{10} R(i, s)$ and embed every $R(i)$ into \mathbb{R}^2 with principal component analysis [12]. However, this can hide the differences in behavior of the hyper-heuristics. A possible explanation is that $R(i_1, s_1)$ and $R(i_1, s_2)$ are almost as different from each other as $R(i_2, s_1)$ and $R(i_1, s_2)$ (see Table I), with $i_1 \neq i_2$ and $s_1 \neq s_2$.

Linear Discriminant Analysis [13], [14] (LDA) overcomes this limitation. First, we fit the LDA with every $R(i, s)$ and set i as the class. The LDA will try to maximize the distance between every two $R(i, s)$ with different i and minimize the distance between every two $R(i, s)$ with the same i . Once we have fitted the LDA, we project every $R(i)$ in the embedded space.

Notice that the LDA takes into account which training problem was used to produce each $R(i, s)$, but it gets no information about the properties of the training problem i : every problem is equal for the LDA. This is an important point because it means that a projection obtained from the LDA does not require this information, and thus, it can be used in the clustering

of unlabeled optimization problems or even the classification of previously unseen optimization problems.

APPENDIX E CHOOSING THE HYPERPARAMETERS

In this Appendix, we justify each of the hyperparameters of the hyper-heuristic (shown in the box below).

Hyper-Heuristic parameters

- Population size: 8
- Stopping criterion: 400 evaluations

Training parameters (NEAT)

- Population size: 10^3 (default value [15])
- Stopping criteria: 4 days or 2000 generations (stop when either criterion is met)

Testing parameters

- Executions averaged: 10^4

Hyper-Heuristic parameters: Population size: 8

We conducted an experiment to choose a suitable population size. We trained and tested the hyper-heuristic on the continuous problem A_1 ⁵, as well as on the Quadratic Assignment Problem instance *Tai60a* from the QAPlib [16], with the hyper-heuristic's population size set to 4, 8, 16, and 32. We repeated the experiment 10 times and show the results in Figure 2 below.

In the continuous problem, the best performing population size was 32, which is also the worst performing population size in the combinatorial problem. This suggests that there is no one size fits all for the population size of the hyper-heuristic, each problem might have a different optimal population size. We believe that the purpose of this paper is not to maximize the objective value in each problem, instead, we want to experiment on the hyper-heuristic as a framework that is applicable in different domains. Following this idea, we think it is desirable to use the same parameters for all problems. A population size of 16 has the second best performance in both problems, however, it has very bad performing outliers in the combinatorial problem. Therefore, we choose a population size of 8, which is the best performing population size for the combinatorial problem.

⁵The objective function of problem A_1 is $f(x_1, \dots, x_{20}) = \sum x_i^2$ as defined in Section IV-A in the main manuscript

(b) Permutation problem $Tai60a$

Figure 2: Objective value of the hyper-heuristic when trained and tested in the same problem. The experiment was repeated 10 times with different seeds. Higher is better.

Hyper-Heuristic parameters: Stopping criterion: 400

A stopping criterion of 400 evaluations with a population size of 8 implies 50 generations, which we think is a reasonable amount. A higher number of evaluations obviously has associated a better objective value (the performance can only increase with additional evaluations), hence a parameter tuning makes no sense with this parameter.

Note that a stopping criterion that is either too small or too large will create problems in the problem analysis methodology. For example, if we use 8 as the stopping criterion, the hyper-heuristic will only do one generation, which means that the algorithm is basically random search (with a budget of 8 solutions). This means that there is no learning to be done, and thus the problem analysis methods will not work. Similarly, with an hypothetical stopping criterion of ∞ solutions, even random search will find the optimal value, and the problem analysis will also fail in this case, as no learning is necessary.

Based on the experimental results on the problem analysis methods, we can empirically say that a stopping criterion of

400 works well.

Training parameters (NEAT): Population size: 10^3

This is the default value, which seems to work well. We think that using the default value in this case is reasonable, as the goal of the paper is not to maximize the performance, but rather to introduce a hyper-heuristic framework.

Stopping criteria: 4 days or 2000 generations (stop when either criterion is met)

This stopping criteria is associated to the maximum runtime of a job in our cluster. We also use 2000 generations as a secondary stopping criterion to ensure that the hyper-heuristic is not trained for more generations in problems with a more computationally efficient objective function. As an example, $A_1 : \sum_{i=1}^d x_i^2$ evaluates faster than $A_{12} : -20 \exp\left(\frac{1}{5}\sqrt{\frac{1}{d}\sum_{i=1}^d x_i^2}\right) - \exp\left(\frac{1}{d}\sum_{i=1}^d \cos(2\pi x_i)\right)$.

Testing parameters: Executions averaged: 10^4 :

The theoretical ideal parameter would be ∞ , which is (by definition) the expected value. Many authors use as little as 20 samples when averaging the results, so if anything, 10^4 would be overkill and is definitely enough. As a reference, Hong et al. [11] use 50 samples in their analysis, which is likely enough as well. We used 10^4 to be absolutely sure that there are no problems with too few samples.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. O. Stanley and R. Miikkulainen, "Evolving Neural Networks through Augmenting Topologies," *Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 99–127, Jun. 2002.
- [2] J. D. Schaffer, D. Whitley, and L. J. Eshelman, "Combinations of genetic algorithms and neural networks: A survey of the state of the art," in *COGANN-92: International Workshop on Combinations of Genetic Algorithms and Neural Networks*. IEEE, 1992, pp. 1–37.
- [3] K. O. Stanley and R. Miikkulainen, "Competitive Coevolution through Evolutionary Complexification," *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research*, vol. 21, pp. 63–100, Feb. 2004.
- [4] F. Gomez, J. Schmidhuber, and R. Miikkulainen, "Accelerated neural evolution through cooperatively coevolved synapses," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 9, no. May, pp. 937–965, 2008.
- [5] P. Pagliuca, N. Milano, and S. Nolfi, "Maximizing adaptive power in neuroevolution," in *PLoS One*, 2018.
- [6] H. Moriguchi and S. Honiden, "CMA-TWEANN: Efficient optimization of neural networks via self-adaptation and seamless augmentation," in *Proceedings of the Fourteenth International Conference on Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference - GECCO '12*. Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, USA: ACM Press, 2012, p. 903.
- [7] Y. Sun, G. G. Yen, and Z. Yi, "Evolving Unsupervised Deep Neural Networks for Learning Meaningful Representations," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 89–103, Feb. 2019.
- [8] F. E. Fernandes Junior and G. G. Yen, "Particle swarm optimization of deep neural networks architectures for Image classification," *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, p. S2210650218309246, Jun. 2019.
- [9] K. O. Stanley, D. B. D'Ambrosio, and J. Gauci, "A Hypercube-Based Encoding for Evolving Large-Scale Neural Networks," *Artificial Life*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 185–212, Apr. 2009.
- [10] T. Schiavinotto and T. Stützle, "A review of metrics on permutations for search landscape analysis," *Computers & operations research*, vol. 34, no. 10, pp. 3143–3153, 2007.
- [11] L. Hong, J. H. Drake, J. R. Woodward, and E. Özcan, "A hyper-heuristic approach to automated generation of mutation operators for evolutionary programming," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 62, pp. 162–175, Jan. 2018.

- [12] S. Wold, K. Esbensen, and P. Geladi, "Principal component analysis," *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems*, vol. 2, no. 1-3, pp. 37–52, Aug. 1987.
- [13] P. Singh, "Dimensionality reduction approaches," <https://towardsdatascience.com/dimensionality-reduction-approaches-8547c4c44334>, 2020-08-18, 2020.
- [14] C. R. Rao, "The utilization of multiple measurements in problems of biological classification," *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 159–203, 1948.
- [15] P. Dougherty, "Accneat," 2014.
- [16] R. E. Burkard, S. E. Karisch, and F. Rendl, "QAPLIB—a quadratic assignment problem library," *Journal of Global optimization*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 391–403, 1997.